

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF A CONTINUOUS FIBRE
REINFORCED TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

BP has consolidated C/TiB₂-coated SiC monofilament in a Ti-6Al-4V matrix. The composite shows strength greater than 1700 MPa and a stiffness of 210 GPa. Exposure to 865°C in vacuum leads to little strength loss after 3.25 hours. This paper also studies the strength of the composite after longer exposures at this temperature, and relates it to fracture behaviour.

Keywords: MMC; Titanium Matrix; Silicon Carbide; Tensile; Strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Titanium matrix composites (TMCs) will give weight savings in many aerospace applications by providing higher specific strength and stiffness than unreinforced alloys (1-2). Monofilament reinforcement offers the greatest potential benefit, with silicon carbide regarded as the leading candidate (3). Uncoated SiC monofilament reacts with titanium alloys during composite production and use at high temperature. This prevents theoretical strength being achieved (4). It is therefore well-established that some form of protective fibre coating is necessary.

BP produces SiC monofilament with a carbon/titanium diboride coating. The inner C-layer increases the strength of the fibre and decreases its strength variation. In the composite it acts to isolate the fibre mechanically from any brittle reaction products. The outer TiB₂-layer acts to inhibit reactions between the C-layer and the matrix. However, the interface is not in equilibrium. Severe thermal exposure leads to changes in the interfacial microstructure and consequent loss of strength in the composite. The work described here attempts to quantify this reaction and highlights related changes in the fracture behaviour, defining process and use windows for the fibre.

2. MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENT

C/TiB₂-coated SiC monofilament was produced by BP Metal Composites Ltd. 75 μ m Ti-6Al-4V foil was obtained from IMI Titanium Ltd. The 6-ply, unidirectional composite panels were prepared by BP (DWA Inc) by vacuum hot-pressing a lay-up of foils and fibre mats.

Mechanical testing was performed on an Instron 4505 test machine with an Instron Series IX data logging and analysis system. Fractography and metallography were carried out using a Hitachi S-2300 SEM operating at an accelerating voltage of 25 kV.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

Tensile testing was based on ASTM D-3552 (5). Parallel sided test coupons, measuring 150x12 mm were prepared using a silicon carbide slitting wheel. Specimens for thermal exposure were wrapped in molybdenum foil and sealed in silica tubes at a pressure of 10⁻⁵ torr. A heat-treatment temperature of 865°C was chosen to allow a rapid evaluation of the effects of thermal exposure on composite strength, and probably represents a temperature at least 100°C above that at which the material would be used in service. Details of the heat-treatments are given in table 1. Tapered aluminium alloy end tabs were applied to the coupons using an epoxy adhesive, leaving a gauge length of 90 mm. Electrical resistance strain gauges were used - one applied to each side of the coupon to compensate for any bending during

the tests. The coupons were tested to failure at a strain rate of $8.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. One specimen, E1077B, was loaded to 90% of its ultimate tensile strength and then unloaded. It was subsequently tested to failure, and differences in the stress/strain curve noted.

Fracture surfaces were examined by SEM. The heat-treated specimens were sectioned, ground and polished using conventional metallographic techniques. The interfaces were then examined by SEM.

4. RESULTS

The mechanical property data is summarised in table 1. A typical stress-strain curve for the as-fabricated composite is shown in figure 1. It consists of two linear regions joined by a short intermediate curved section. A fracture surface of an as-fabricated sample is shown in figure 2. This shows pull-out of the monofilaments, and ductile failure of the matrix. The stress-strain curve for specimen E1077B is shown in figure 3. On reloading this specimen, the initial gradient is unchanged. Also, the deviation from linearity of the reloading curve occurs at 0.65% strain, whereas in the initial loading curve it occurs at 0.4% strain.

The fracture surfaces of specimens 6A and 26A are shown in figures 4 and 5. Although these specimens, like the as-fabricated composite, show ductile failure of the matrix, the degree of fibre pull-out is much smaller. The progressive strength loss of the composite with heat-treatment is shown in figure 6. Figure 7 shows metallographic sections of the interface from the as-fabricated composite and from specimens 6A and 26A. In specimen 6A there were no areas where the C-layer had been completely consumed. In specimen 26A there were many areas where the C-layer had been consumed, and obvious attack of the silicon carbide had begun.

5. DISCUSSION

It has been suggested that the knee in the stress/strain curve of SiC monofilament reinforced TMCs represents the onset of fibre fracture. The results from specimen E1077B suggest that this interpretation does not

apply to BP's material. Fibre fracture would lead to a loss of modulus on unloading and reloading, which was not seen. The knee is more likely to be due to matrix yielding caused by a combination of the applied stress and internal stress due to differential thermal contraction.

Support for this interpretation comes from the fact that the second linear region of the stress/strain curve has a gradient approximately equal to the stiffness of the monofilament multiplied by its volume fraction. This suggests that little matrix work-hardening is taking place. Further tests including acoustic emission monitoring will be carried out to clarify this matter.

The heat-treated specimens show that this composite has a useful lifetime somewhere between 3.25 and 6.5 hours at 865°C. An activation energy for the interfacial reaction, derived from studies at different temperatures, can be used to predict the composite life at service temperatures. For example an activation energy of 350 kJ/mol (recently measured by BP for the reaction of the C-layer) gives an equivalent lifetime greater than 1500 hours at 700°C. If, as is likely, the life is limited by diffusion, doubling the thickness of the carbon layer should increase the life by a factor of 4.

Strength loss occurs before complete consumption of the C-layer. This has implications for prediction of composite properties from microstructural studies (6). The decrease in fibre pull-out could be associated with a change in the fibre strength and strength distribution or with a change in the interface properties, or both. Measurements of interfacial mechanical properties, and tests on extracted fibres are needed to explore this further.

6. CONCLUSIONS

BP can fabricate composites with strength in excess of 1700 MPa and stiffness of 210 GPa. The yield point on the stress/strain curve of this material is associated with matrix yielding rather than with fibre breakage. When heat-treated at temperatures well above projected use

temperatures it was found that strength reduction and changes in fracture morphology occurred ahead of obvious microstructural degradation. Further work is required to understand fully the mechanical behaviour and mechanisms of strength loss in these composites.

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TABLE 1 HEAT-TREATMENTS AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Specimen ID	Time at 865°C	Volume Fraction	UTS	Modulus	Elongation
	(Hr)	(%)	(MPa)	(GPa)	(%)
E1077A	None	38	1822	211	1.03
			1761	209	— ^a
			1641	204	0.95
			1708	209	0.87
			1747	216	0.99
			1757	210	0.99
E1077B	None	38	1708	209	0.83
E1079/0	None	38	1709	— ^b	—
E1080/0	None	38	1608	—	—
E1079/3	3.25	38	1400	—	—
E1080/3	3.25	38	1636	—	—
E1079/6	6.5	38	1240	—	—
E1080/6	6.5	38	1178	—	—
E1079/13	13	38	937	—	—
E1080/13	13	38	923	—	—
E1079/26	26	38	736	—	—
E1080/26	26	38	893	—	—

(a) Elongation could not be measured for this specimen due to premature failure of the strain gauge.

(b) Strain measurements were not carried out during testing of the series of heat-treated specimens.

Figure 1. Stress/strain curve for as-fabricated composite.

200 μm

Figure 2. Fracture surface of as-fabricated composite.

Figure 3. Stress/strain curve for as-fabricated composite, showing effect of unloading and reloading.

200 μm

Figure 4. Composite fracture surface after 6.5 hours at 865°C.

200 μm

Figure 5. Composite fracture surface after 26 hours at 865°C.

Figure 6. Composite strength as a function of time at 865°C.

Figure 7. Composite interface: (a) as-fabricated; (b) after 6.5 hours at 865°C; (c) after 26 hours at 865°C.